
Activation Addition: Steering Language Models Without Optimization

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Abstract

Reliably controlling the behavior of large language models is a pressing open problem. Existing methods include supervised finetuning, reinforcement learning from human feedback, prompt engineering and guided decoding. We instead investigate activation engineering: modifying activations at inference-time to predictably alter model behavior. We bias the forward pass with a ‘steering vector’ implicitly specified through natural language. Past work (Subramani et al., 2022; Hernandez et al., 2023) learned these steering vectors; our Activation Addition (ActAdd) method instead computes them by taking activation differences resulting from pairs of prompts. We demonstrate ActAdd on GPT-2 and replicate on Llama-13B and GPT-J-6B, testing on perplexity, toxicity, and sentiment. Our approach yields inference-time control over high-level properties of output & preserves performance off-target. It takes far less compute/implementation than finetuning, allows natural language specification by users, and its overhead scales naturally with model size.

1. Introduction

The success of large language models (LLMs) pretrained on massive corpora (Peters et al., 2018; Devlin et al., 2018; Radford et al., 2019; Brown et al., 2020) comes with a large caveat: our ability to control the output of these models remains partial & computationally expensive. Controls include supervised finetuning (Devlin et al., 2018), reinforcement learning from human feedback (RLHF) (Ziegler et al., 2019), prompt engineering (Radford et al., 2019), & guided decoding (Ghazvininejad et al., 2017; Gu et al., 2017).

We instead investigate controlling LLMs with minimal computational overhead, by modifying their activations. We call this approach *activation engineering*, as pioneered by Subramani et al. 2022 and Hernandez et al. 2023. We go further by demonstrating *natural-language* control of activations and thereby output text. We use pairs of prompts to implicitly specify a direction in activation space which we scale to control the model (sentiment, truthfulness, but also topic and style; see Appendix Table 5). In contrast with past

work (Shen et al., 2017; Dathathri et al., 2020; Subramani et al., 2022; Li et al., 2023b), ActAdd does not require labelled data (except prompts) nor backward passes to learn an encoder, controller, classifier or activation direction.

Table 1. Output before (‘None’) & after applying ActAdd. The steering vectors used are (Love – Hate) and (I talk about weddings constantly – I do not talk about weddings constantly).

Prompt	+ steering	= completion
I hate you because	[None]	...you are the most disgusting thing I have ever seen.
	ActAdd (love)	...you are so beautiful and I want to be with you forever.
I went up to my friend and said	[None]	“I’m sorry, I can’t help you.” “No,” he said. “You’re not.”
	ActAdd (weddings)	“I’m going to talk about the wedding in this episode of Wedding Season. I think it’s a really good episode. It’s about how you’re supposed to talk about weddings.”

We make four main contributions: 1) We find that combining forward passes (adding activation vectors) works well in LLMs despite the model not being trained for this; 2) We develop a lightweight control method, **Activation Additions** (ActAdd), which works at inference time and requires *no* optimization or labelled data. This is thus a promising direction for user control of LLMs; 3) We show that ActAdd preserves model performance, involves far less compute and implementation (vs finetuning and RLHF), scales naturally with model size, while being easier to implement; 4) We compare ActAdd against several baselines and observe competitive results on sentiment control.

2. Related Work

2.1. Latent space arithmetic

Research in generative models for computer vision has long demonstrated the ability to steer image generation using derived vectors, including steering latent variables – most famously, intervening on a dimension that corresponds to smiles in images (Larsen et al., 2016; White, 2016).

Similarly, in the text domain, classic results on the word2vec embedding show that arithmetic on word vectors can capture some parts of semantic reasoning (for instance, analogies) (Mikolov et al., 2013b;a). Our work differs in being computed (with forward passes) rather than learned (with backward passes); in operating on activation space, rather than embedding or weight space; and in presenting a natural-language user interface.

2.2. LLM steering

Many approaches attempt to affect the output of a pretrained LLM, whether:

- *Intervening on weights*, as with supervised fine-tuning, RLHF, steerable layers, and weight editing (that is, targeted fine-tuning) (Ranzato et al., 2016; Ziegler et al., 2019; Dathathri et al., 2020; Meng et al., 2023; Ilharco et al., 2023). However, RLHF and weight editing have known side-effects on overall model performance (OpenAI, 2023; Hase et al., 2023; Brown et al., 2023);
- *Intervening at decoding*, as with guided or trainable decoding (Gu et al., 2017; Grover et al., 2019) (See Zhang et al. 2022 for an overview of controlled generation and Jin et al. 2022 for textual style transfer.);
- *Intervening on the prompt*, as with automated prompt engineering (Shin et al., 2020; Zhou et al., 2022) and soft or continuous prompting (Lester et al., 2021; Li & Liang, 2021);
- *Intervening on token embeddings*, as with ‘soft prompting’ (Li & Liang, 2021; Lester et al., 2021; Khashabi et al., 2022);
- *Intervening on activations*, for instance by freezing the weights of the LLM and searching for a ‘steering vector’ of activations, e.g. using gradient descent (Subramani et al., 2022; Hernandez et al., 2023). These optimized extraction methods, which search for a steering vector, differ from extraction methods which directly compute it (present work and Li et al. 2023b). We now elaborate on this family of methods.

Table 2. Locating our work in the steering vector literature.

Steering vectors via	Intervenes on model...	
	... weights	... activations
Differences after fine-tuning	Ilharco 2023	N/A
Per-query gradient-based search	Meng 2022, Orgad 2023	Dathathri 2020 Subramani 2022 Hernandez 2023
Differences in truthy attention heads	N/A	Li 2023b
Differences between prompt pairs	N/A	ActAdd (present work)

2.3. Activation engineering

Activation (or representation) engineering involves creating vectors of activations which cause desired changes to output text when added to the forward passes of a frozen LLM (Dathathri et al., 2020; Zou et al., 2023). (Table 2 organizes prior work by intervention type.) An early antecedent of the approach is the Plug-and-Play Language Model of Dathathri et al. 2020. This uses a separate classifier (one classifier per attribute to steer towards) to perturb the model’s activations to generate text that accords more closely with the classifier’s target.

Subramani et al. 2022 extract latent steering vectors from a frozen LLM, successfully discovering sentence-specific vectors which steer completions to near-perfect BLEU scores (i.e. control of the LLM’s generation) and unsupervised style transfer. However, the method requires running gradient descent for each new steering vector.

Inference-Time Intervention (ITI) (Li et al., 2023b) independently developed a similar method which computes steering vectors (though not without some prior optimization). They use linear probe accuracy to find attention heads with different activation distributions for true and false statements (which requires labelled data, in this case TruthfulQA, to operationalize ‘truth’). The authors intervene on these heads to steer the model toward truthful output, where our experiments cover a range of goals without needing labelled data.

Figure 1. Schematic of the Activation Addition (ActAdd) method. \circ = natural language text; \bullet = vectors of activations just before a specified layer. In this example, the output is heavily biased towards discussing weddings, regardless of the topic of the user prompt. (See Algorithm 1 for omitted parameters over intervention strength, intervention layer, and sequence alignment.)

In addition, ITI is repeated at each next-token prediction and requires dozens-to-hundreds of samples; suitable prompts can be found for ActAdd in as few as 2 samples. Similar work on In-context Vectors also followed ours (Liu et al., 2023).

Hernandez et al. 2023 locate and edit an LLM’s knowledge through learning an encoding of facts in its activation space. Ablating attention heads can also be seen as activation engineering, though the technique is mostly used for model interpretation rather than steering per se (Michel et al., 2019; Olsson et al., 2022).

3. Methods

3.1. The Transformer architecture

We use decoder-only Transformer neural networks trained on a suitably large text corpus (Vaswani et al., 2017; Liu et al., 2018). The LLMs in this work are a stack of Transformer layers, each consisting of multi-head attention (MHA) and a feedforward network (FFN). We focus on its ‘residual streams’ (Elhage et al., 2021), the sequences $(\mathbf{x}_0, \dots, \mathbf{x}_n)$ of token vectors processed by each layer. GPT-2-XL’s token vectors are 1600-dimensional (Radford et al., 2019). ActAdd manipulates the residual stream values \mathbf{h}^l input to layer l . Following Elhage et al. 2021, we view each MHA block as adding an independent vector into that layer’s residual stream. Each layer performs MHA and FFN computations on \mathbf{x}_i , adding \mathbf{x}_{i+1} to the stream. The final vector \mathbf{x}_n in the stream can then be decoded into the next-token prediction. At inference-time, the residual stream is initialized \mathbf{h}^1 with the embedding of the tokenized prompt.

3.2. Activation addition

Our method takes a pair of natural-language prompts (p_+, p_-) , where p_+ represents the property we wish out-

put text to emphasise and p_- represents its opposite. \mathbf{h}_+^l is the activation vector for the prompt p_+ at layer l . The difference $\mathbf{h}_+^l - \mathbf{h}_-^l$ is a new activation vector which (intuitively) captures the difference between a prompt with the property, and without it. This can be seen as an analogue of the ‘comparative preference statements’ used in recent formal logics (Kaci & Patel, 2014). To obtain a steering vector, we perform a forward pass on each prompt, record the activations at the given location in each pass, take the difference $\mathbf{h}_+^l - \mathbf{h}_-^l$, and then finally rescale this difference in activations by an ‘injection coefficient’ c . To steer, we add the resulting activation vector to the input of layer l and allow the forward pass to continue, and so obtain our steered output. (See Appendix B for implementation details.)

c represents intervention strength, since it multiplies the specified direction’s contribution to the residual stream and so the token processing of the rest of the forward pass. Absolute values between 3 and 15 are typical. Along with the target layer l , c is a free parameter we select via grid search. (We find that, as expected from past work, intervening at middle layers is most effective (Subramani et al., 2022; Turner et al., 2023).)

Algorithm 1 and Figure 1 depict the resulting ActAdd method. Appendix Figure 6 gives a figurative example of steering a model with ActAddif that model had 1-dimensional residual streams (rather than GPT-2-XL’s 1600 dimensions). The method differs from past work in being computed (with forward passes) rather than learned (with backward passes); in operating on activation space rather than embedding space or weight space; in presenting the user a natural-language interface; and in requiring as few as 2 samples in order to find an appropriate prompt pair (‘contrast pair’) to specify the steering direction. (One serious constraint is that the model must cache intermediate activations; see Bloom & Nanda 2022.)

Algorithm 1 ActAdd, optimization-free activation addition

Input: (p_+, p_-) = steering prompt pair, tokenized
 p^* = user prompt
 l = target layer
 c = injection coefficient
 a = sequence position to align \mathbf{h}_A and \mathbf{h}_{p^*}
 M = pretrained language model

Output: S = steered output

$(p'_+, p'_-) \leftarrow \text{pad_right_same_token_len}(p_+, p_-)$
 $\mathbf{h}_+^l \leftarrow M.\text{forward}(p'_+).\text{activations}[l]$
 $\mathbf{h}_-^l \leftarrow M.\text{forward}(p'_-).\text{activations}[l]$
 $\mathbf{h}_A^l \leftarrow \mathbf{h}_+^l - \mathbf{h}_-^l$
 $\mathbf{h}^l \leftarrow M.\text{forward}(p^*).\text{activations}[l]$
 $S \leftarrow M.\text{continue_forward}(c\mathbf{h}_A^l + \mathbf{h}^l @ a)$

The contrast pair (p^+, p^-) can be of arbitrary lengths (empirically, right-padding the shorter prompt using whitespace gives good results).

Interestingly, our steering vectors are not specified by taking the difference between desired outputs (e.g. “John married Jane” vs “John hired Jane”). It is instead more analogous to ‘preference statements’ (Kaci & Patel, 2014). Both prompts (p_+, p_-) are (say) wedding-related: “I love talking about weddings” and “I hate talking about weddings”. That this would lead to more steering toward the wedding topic is not a trivial fact, since both prompts talk about weddings and the instance of ‘wedding’ in p_- becomes part of a vector which gets penalized. So ActAdd works above token-level.

Further implementation details can be found in Appendix C. See also Appendix H for a partial variant of ActAdd. A runnable notebook can be found at tinyurl.com/actadd.

Some desirable properties of a steering method include: effectiveness at steering output; generality (ability to affect any aspect of the output, e.g. sentiment, topic, style, knowledge, or role); ease of specification; low computational overhead; and no side effects on unsteered parts of the model. We design experiments to test ActAdd on these desiderata (see Results). Our main experiments use GPT-2-XL (1.5B parameters) (Radford et al., 2019), but the method scales well, see Figure 5 and our informal experiments with LLaMA-7B and -13B (Table 12).¹

3.3. Metrics

Perplexity ratio For each document $d_i \in D$ in OpenWebText, we first calculate the frequency of wedding-related

¹The full repo with all experiments can be found at <https://zenodo.org/records/8215277>; see also <http://tinyurl.com/actadd3-llama> for experiments on larger models. See Appendix C for reproducibility and D for replication.

words (‘wedding’, ‘weddings’, ‘wed’, ‘marry’, ‘married’, ‘marriage’, ‘bride’, ‘groom’, ‘honeymoon’), $f_w(d_i)$. Any document with > 0 wedding-related words is considered wedding-related. We randomly sample 300k documents - half wedding-related and half unrelated. The only pre-processing performed is to remove sequences of null characters. Each document is split into sentences $s_j \in d_i$ using the Punkt tokenizer (Strunk, 2013).

For each resulting sentence we calculate the log-probabilities $\mathcal{L}(t_k)$ for each token $t_k \in s_j$ under the unmodified M_{baseline} and modified M_{ActAdd} models.²

We take the mean over tokens, resulting in a mean token log-probability $\bar{\mathcal{L}}(d_i, M)$ for each document and model. We then group documents by their wedding-word frequency f_w (e.g. ‘those with 0.5% to 1% of their tokens wedding-related’; ‘those with 1 to 1.5% of their tokens wedding-related’), producing bins of documents b_m . We calculate the mean difference in token log-probabilities

$$\bar{X}(b_m) = \text{mean}_{d_i \in b_m} (\bar{\mathcal{L}}(d_i, M_{\text{ActAdd}}) - \bar{\mathcal{L}}(d_i, M_{\text{baseline}}))$$

for each bin. (We use only bins with a number of documents $|b_m| > 1000$, to reduce sampling noise.)

Finally, the change in perplexity under ActAdd for each wedding-word-frequency bin is

$$\text{PerplexityRatio}(b_m) = -\exp(\bar{X}(b_m))$$

Shift in logprobs To test if the intervention is affecting relevant tokens or reducing perplexity in some spurious way, we observe the shift in the distribution of token log probabilities. We do this by randomly sampling 500 documents from the above OpenWebText sample and recording the log-probabilities assigned by the baseline and ActAdded models. (This results in a dataset of 500k tokens, of which 29k are unique.) We then group by token, filter for tokens with >20 instances in the dataset, and calculate the mean \mathcal{L} difference between the ActAdd and baseline models. We display these as a Q-Q plot (Gnanadesikan & Wilk, 1968) (i.e. compare the distribution quantile values) and inspect outlier tokens.

Inference time premium We wish to measure how much overhead ActAdd adds to inference. To obtain the percentage increase in time-to-complete one forward pass using ActAdd for different model sizes, we iterate over a list of models of different sizes and 10 random seeds. We obtain a baseline inference time for each (model, seed) pair through 100 repeated forward passes on a batch of random tokens (32 sequences of length 64). We obtain an ActAdd inference

²We mask the stream positions where the activation addition takes place, so to consider only next-token predictions coming from positions *not* directly modified by the intervention.

time for each (model, seed) pair by running the previous method, augmented by a test ActAdd contrast pair: ‘This is a test prompt.’ (p_+) and the empty string (p_-). Running a batch-of-2 forward pass on these gets us the activation addition tensor, which we add at layer 6. We take the mean inference time \bar{t} over the 10 random seeds, and calculate the inference time premium as

$$\text{premium} = \frac{\bar{t}_{\text{ActAdd}}}{\bar{t}_{\text{baseline}}} - 1.$$

Relevance steering To demonstrate general topic steering, we test a range of subjects against a generic prompt, and use GPT-3.5 to score modified and unmodified model completions on whether they relate to the ActAdd topic (i.e. whether steering worked).

The procedure: we generate 100 prompt completions from the unmodified model; iterate over a list of single-token topic ActAdds, applying each and generating 100 more completions; for each completion, we evaluate relevance to the topic using GPT-3.5. (The completions from the unmodified model are evaluated for relevance to each topic, to provide a relevance baseline; the modified-model completions are evaluated for relevance to the intended steering topic). Finally, we aggregate these evaluations for each (topic, coefficient) pair to get a mean relevance fraction, and subtract the baseline relevance.

The prompt used for all completions is: Did you know that

The evaluation template: Is this text related to {topic}? Answer either ‘yes’ or ‘no’

Text {prompt_with_completion}
Answer:

Generation scoring To show the effect of different injection layers and give a sense of the reliability of ActAdd, we score the generations as follows. We generate a batch of completions for a specific prompt p , both with and without ActAdd, and computed average number of related words and fraction of completions with a related word over the resulting completions.

The following settings are the *only* iteration run for this experiment:

$$p^* = \text{‘I went up to my friend and said’}$$

$$p^+ = \text{‘weddings’}, p_- = \text{‘ ’}, c = 1.0, \text{seed} = 0$$

Completion length is 40 tokens with model sampling parameters: temperature = 1, frequency penalty = 1, top-P = 0.3. For each setting, we compute statistics over a batch of 200 completions. Wedding-relatedness is operationalized as before. Finally we sweep over all layers (i.e. 1 - 48).

Preservation of performance, P@K We also test that ActAdd does not disrupt the model’s general knowledge (as some other steering methods do). We use ConceptNet from the LAMA benchmark, a general knowledge dataset ($n = 29774$ sentences, see Appendix Table 9). The test data involves prompting the model and filling the gap with the expected entity. The task is intended for both causal and masked models, so some examples are difficult for ‘causal’ models (like GPT-2) due to the extremely limited context.

Our evaluation procedure follows the original LAMA procedure: we load all sentences and extract the prompt and expected label. To simplify evaluation, we remove sentences with an expected label that tokenizes to more than one token. For each sentence, we run the model on its prompt with and without the wedding activation addition. $P@K$ is the probability that the expected label is among the model’s top- K predicted tokens, conditioned on the prompt. We score the baseline and modified models by calculating mean $P@K$ values for a range of K . Finally we plot these for both modified and unmodified models over a range of K values.

Sentiment steering To evaluate sentiment we use the Stanford IMDB dataset (Maas et al., 2011), the goal of which is continuations with a sentiment *opposite* to that of the prompt. ‘Success’ is here the proportion of generated outputs with the desired sentiment, as classified by a model finetuned on sentiment data, SiBERT (Hartmann et al., 2023). For quality controls, we follow the conventional use of conditional perplexity to mark fluency, obtained using the GPT-3 davinci-002 logprobs. And cosine similarity between the prompt and continuation sentence embeddings to gauge the relevance of text in [0,1].³

With a random subset $n = 1000$, we perform this evaluation for both sentiment changes from positive to negative and viceversa. We repeat this to obtain p-values.

Toxicity We benchmark toxicity reduction by generating steered continuations from RealToxicityPrompts (Gehman et al., 2020). Following Pei et al. 2023 we use a random subset $n = 1000$. We repeat this sampling to obtain p -values (one-sample t -test against the unsteered baseline). For each continuation, we use the Perspective API⁴ to score toxicity (lower better).⁵

4. Results

Natural-language control of sentiment, topic, style We report some illustrative results in Table 1 and Appendix

³Our sentiment steering code is at tinyurl.com/actadd-sent

⁴<https://perspectiveapi.com/>

⁵Our toxicity experiments are at tinyurl.com/actadd-tox.

Table 5, including vectors for inducing anger (sentiment steering), weddings (topic steering), and conspiracy theories (topic/style steering). These completions were all obtained through one run of top-3 sampling. In particular, note the `Eiffel` vector (fact editing reminiscent of the ROME method (Meng et al., 2023)), the range of sentiments and styles induced, and (to a weaker extent) the alignment (see the `Hurt` vector in Appendix Table 5). A runnable notebook with all examples is at tinyurl.com/actadd3.

Intervention effectiveness To evaluate how effectively ActAdd steers output, we test extensively on the OpenWebText corpus (Peterson et al., 2018). Our running concrete example is the impact of the “wedding” topic vector produced by setting $p_+ = \text{weddings}$ and $p_- = \cdot$, $l = 16$, $c = 1$). (See ‘Generality’ below for broader tests.)

Experiment 1: perplexity ratio. First we check that ActAdd increases the probability of the model outputting tokens related to the wedding vector. Appendix Figure 7 shows the resulting perplexity ratios under ActAdd, relative to the unmodified model. On documents where the injected topic is more relevant, ActAdd’s relative predictive performance increases.

Experiment 2: logprob distribution shift. However, is the intervention affecting the tokens we expect it to, or is it reducing perplexity in some spurious way?

Appendix Figure 9 shows the resulting mean log-probability difference distribution. We see that is approximately normal for the bulk of the tokens but with clearly heavy tails. The positive tail is significantly heavier than the negative tail, suggesting that one set of tokens are reliably increased in probability, with a smaller set of tokens reliably decreased to a lesser extent.

The outlier tokens can be found in Appendix Table 10. From this we see clearly that the probabilities most increased on average are primarily wedding-related. The bottom tokens share no obvious theme and show a significantly lower absolute change in probability.

Experiment 3: generation-scoring.

Figure 2 and Appendix Figure 8 show the result of sweeping the ActAdd intervention over layers and taking the count or fraction of related words. We see that the intervention (in this case) is already effective at the very first layer, rises in effectiveness until $l = 6$, and then declines. Note also that for the optimal injection site we see >90% success in steering topic (compared to a ~2% baseline).

Generality The wedding steering vector used above is just a running example to keep the impact concrete. (Averaging over a collection of steering vectors makes it difficult to

Figure 2. Topic steering effect (mean related words in completions) over injection layer. In blue is the average related-word count among 200 ActAdd completions; the dotted line is the count among unmodified completions.

depict the magnitude of the steering.) To show that this topic is not a special case, we also test a range of topics against a generic prompt, and use GPT-3.5 to score relative relevance (i.e. whether steering worked).

The results can be seen in Figure 3: we see a large effect (c. 20% on GPT’s gestalt measure) on all tested broad topics at strength $c = 2$, with the exception of ‘art’.

Sentiment control Our method is competitive on the usual measure of sentiment (Maas et al., 2011). We see a 3x improvement in sentiment control success over an unsteered baseline in Table 3 – exceeding all baselines in the negative-to-positive direction and approaching the best value (PREADD-S) in positive-to-negative. Bold results represent a one-sample t-test $p < 0.05$ compared to the unsteered baseline.

Toxicity reduction To establish a common scale we reused the baselines and PREADD results from Pei et al. (2023), adding results from Zhong et al. (2023) and Gu et al. (2022). This yields 7 baselines to compare ActAdd against. We compare to ActAdd’s results on GPT-2-XL.

In Table 4, we observe a 9% drop in toxicity over an unsteered baseline – comparable to PREADD-S but clearly not matching PREADD-D and PriorControl.

Preservation of general (off-target) performance As shown in Figure 4, using the ConceptNet benchmark of factual questions, our method has a negligible impact on off-target answer probabilities over a range of top- K values.

Table 3. Results on the IMDb sentiment dataset (random n=1000)

Control Type	Method	steering from negative to positive			steering from positive to negative			Model Size
		Success \uparrow	Fluency \downarrow	Relevance \uparrow	Success \uparrow	Fluency \downarrow	Relevance \uparrow	
Steering vector	ActAdd (ours)	0.624	20.7	0.327	0.660	20.3	0.387	1.5B
None	Unsteered OPT	0.168	51.3	0.306	0.141	49.6	0.294	6.7B
Prompting	Simple prompting	0.307	53.5	0.298	0.365	50.9	0.287	6.7B
Controlled generation	FUDGE (k = 100)	0.532	25.1	0.311	0.551	22.7	0.320	6.7B
Contrast decoding	PREADD Static	0.631	68.4	0.253	0.624	67.1	0.258	6.7B

Figure 3. GPT-3.5-scored relevance of ActAdd completions on a range of generic topics.

Algebraic combination of forward passes Every example of ActAdd in this paper (e.g. those in Appendix Table 5) is an example of composing forward passes (e.g. we compose \mathbf{h}_+ , \mathbf{h}_- and \mathbf{h}^* to produce steered output). This forms evidence for compositional representations (Olah, 2023), independent of the evidence from task-composition arithmetic on weights (Ilharco et al., 2023). See Appendices D and E for further experiments into the mechanism of a steering vector.

Scales with model size We lastly wish to estimate the overhead ActAdd adds to inference – in particular the relationship between overhead and model size – to check that the method will remain relevant for massive frontier models and future models.

Because ActAdd involves only forward passes, it scales naturally with model size (Figure 5): the relationship between inference time premium and model size is decreasing.

5. Discussion

Limitations and Broader Impact ActAdd works well in some cases, but it still requires a search for its p_+ , c and l arguments. (So far we have had success with fixing $a = 1$.) This makes it less user-friendly than simple prompt engineering. We include examples of failed steering vectors in Appendix Table 6; in particular, we lack understanding of when large injection coefficients damage capabilities. Further, even in its 1.5B form, GPT-2 is not sophisticated enough to support any demonstration of the effect of ActAdd on reasoning tasks. ActAdd still has two free parameters, the injection coefficient and the target layer, and if these values were very sensitive to the desired contrast pair then the method would suffer some computational overhead. But in practice we find that reusing these hyperparameters works well for a given frozen model and level of abstraction in the task. Finally, the LLM used must both cache and expose intermediate activations at the given layer Bloom &

Table 4. Results on RealToxicityPrompts (random n=1000)

Control Type	Method	Toxicity ↓	Fluency ↓	Relevance ↑	Model size
Steering vector	ActAdd (ours)	.140	12.0	.324	1.5B
None	Unsteered OPT	.152	49.9	.301	6.7B
Prompting	Simple prompting	.200	54.3	.294	6.7B
Controlled generation	FUDGE (k = 100)	.128	22.1	.329	6.7B
Contrast decoding	PREADD-S	.134	51.7	.290	6.7B
Contrast decoding	PREADD-D	.122	56.6	.326	6.7B
Gradient-guided generation	Air-Decoding	.185	48.3	-	355M
Gradient-guided generation	PriorControl	.043	54.6	-	345M

Figure 4. Testing side effects of ActAdd with the ConceptNet benchmark (Petroni et al., 2019), a general relational knowledge dataset. ‘P@K’ is the probability of the correct answer being in the model’s top K answers. Our method has a negligible impact on off-target probabilities across a range of top-K values.

Nanda 2022, which rules out user control of commercial models (though backend use is still possible). As the examples of anger- and conspiracy-steering show (Appendix Table 5), ActAdd can easily be misused. Insofar as existing methods for steering LLMs leave the target goal or property somewhere in the model (but simply make it low probability), activation engineering may circumvent superficial alignment methods.

Activation engineering vs fine-tuning The first advantage of ActAdd is simple efficiency: the method requires no backward passes and can thus run on any machine that can perform inference rather than training (which, for frontier models, is millions of times more computationally demanding (Fuller, 2022)). Implementation effort is also greatly reduced; only forward passes are required to find a suitable (p_+, p_-) and no labelled data is required (let alone the hun-

Figure 5. The cost to inference speed of ActAdd over increasing model size, as measured by the % increase in inference time. We see that the relationship is decreasing (in the GPT family) over an order of magnitude increase in parameter count (124M to 2.7B).

dreds of examples of normal finetuning). We discovered most of the example contrast pairs in Appendix Table 5 in minutes. Together, these mean that even nontechnical users can benefit from rapid feedback with roughly the same difficulty as hand-crafted prompt engineering.

Following Sloman 2002, we distinguish ‘ballistic’ steering (which steers the model once, e.g. at train time) from ‘on-line’ steering (which can steer the model repeatedly, e.g. at inference time). Fine-tuning is ballistic, while ActAdd is online in this sense - which enables iteration and otherwise infeasible chains and mixes of steering decisions.

Activation additions may preserve model interpretability, even while changing the model’s alignment. When fine-tuning a model, a single gradient update can change every parameter in it, thereby undoing your prior interpretability work, which depends on tracking individual neurons and

circuits of neurons. By contrast, activation additions leave weights unchanged. If you can understand what the weights implement, and something about the activation additions, you can preserve your understanding of the steered model.

Finally, we hypothesize that activation addition may allow control over properties inaccessible to the fine-tuning process. The intuition is that since the *currently-active* goal is contextual, it depends more on short-lived activations than the weights (which instead represent some analogue of skills and other stable patterns and *mixtures* of possible goals). Future work could compare ActAdd on knowledge editing benchmarks (Wu et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2024). (The comparison could be unfair to methods like ROME (Meng et al., 2023), since our method is not editing weights, but it would give standardized evidence about steering.)

Activation engineering vs prompt engineering Activation additions can be continuously weighted, while prompts are discrete (since a token is either present, or not). To more intensely steer the model to generate wedding-related text, our method does not require any edit to the prompt, but instead just increasing the injection coefficient. See Appendix A for suggestive experiments on ActAdd vs prompting. Unlike the use of extensive ‘meta-prompts’ (prepended natural language specifications), activation additions do not take up token space in the model’s context window, and thus reduce another kind of steering overhead.

We argue that activation additions *generalize* prompt engineering (by allowing weights on token embeddings). Our current understanding of prompting suggests that they too work by activating some goals preferentially (by conditioning the model on one part of activation space). But we hypothesize that activation additions may allow the user to affect properties inaccessible to prompts (see Appendix A).

Interpretability of LLMs In most programs, adding values to imprecisely-targeted intermediate memory locations would not yield sensible results. Why expect this from Transformers? A growing consensus in mechanistic interpretability is that the activation space of an LLM contains directions which represent high-level latents; moreover, experiments intervening in these directions show that they are causally involved in what is generated (Burns et al., 2022; Moschella et al., 2023; Li et al., 2023a; Nanda, 2023; Li et al., 2023b). Our hypothesis, following Elhage et al. 2022, is more specific: that neural networks represent features of the input as directions in activation space, that is, with a linear representation (Park et al., 2023). Moreover, the direction in activation space that corresponds to (say) a love-hate latent variable stays approximately the *same* across a broad class of inputs, when fixing (p_+, p_-) and varying p^* .

Alain & Bengio 2018 use linear probes on residual streams to infer that LLM representations are at least partially linear; if a linear probe can predict some feature of text output from the residuals with high accuracy, this forms evidence that the feature is represented linearly (i.e. as a simple direction) (Nanda, 2023). However, this observational approach cannot rule out spurious correlations or nonlinear features which behave like linear features when computing the next token. (Linear probes also require a training signal.)

The success of activation addition gives stronger, experimental evidence of feature linearity, demonstrating that models *use* feature-related information. Consider the central Love – Hate vector example: we add it to the forward pass and so increase love-related completions. This implicit direction is thus causally responsible for steering the rest of the model to love-related completions. This echoes prior work by Nanda 2023, Merullo et al. 2023, and contemporaneous work by Park et al. 2023.

Value alignment of LLMs Activation engineering represents a promising mode of interaction with LLMs. Successor methods may be able to provide general steering methods (e.g. through some analogue of a `Be helpful` vector). Alongside contemporaneous work (Li et al., 2023b; Liu et al., 2023), our experiments suggest that activation engineering can flexibly retarget LLM behavior without damaging general performance. We speculate that this involves changing the model’s currently-active (mixture of) goals. Suitably developed, the activation engineering approach could enable safety progress while incurring a very low ‘alignment tax’ – i.e., cost of opting for safety (Askell et al., 2021; Ouyang et al., 2022).

6. Conclusion

Activation addition complements existing prompt engineering and finetuning methods while offering users a novel form of interaction with language models. We demonstrated natural-language control of output sentiment, topic, and style and showed that overall factual performance is preserved after activations are edited. We showed that GPT-2 affords algebraic combination of forward passes. We showed that ActAdd scales very well with model size. Compared to prompt engineering and finetuning, activation engineering has some promising properties, allowing us to compose and reweight model goals at inference time, free up context window space, and allow fast feedback at low computational cost. Our results provide evidence about the computational structure of LLM representations, at least in GPT-2. Future work will scale to larger models, investigate non-natural-language contrast pairs, and explain why adding together intermediate results from forward passes works so well.

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Appendix

(Note: some completions contain unpleasant content, including slurs.)

A. Is ActAdd just a subtle kind of prompt engineering?

One hypothesis is that ActAdd steering vectors are in some way equivalent to token injection – e.g. adding a virtual ‘weddings’ token at the given stream position.

This is plausible for simpler interventions. Given the prompt ‘I love you because’, if we inject a ‘wedding’ token into the first residual stream with a large coefficient, perhaps the model indeed just processes the prompt as ‘wedding love you because’ instead.

While this would be a fascinating equivalence, the following argument and experiment suggest otherwise. Since tokens are discrete, the token injection hypothesis comes apart from the linear representations hypothesis in cases like adding $3 \times$ ‘wedding’ and then $-3 \times$ ‘< whitespace >’, on top of the token ‘I’. Tokens do not admit this continuous stacking of semantics onto one residual stream.

However, consider the steering vector for `Anger – Calm` with $l = 20, c = +10$. We show in Appendix Table 5 that this steering vector appears to make completions angrier. Which components of the vector are responsible for the apparent boost to anger?

Skeptical hypothesis: the anger steering effect is driven less by the computational work done by Transformer blocks 0 through 19, but instead simply the embedding vector component of the steering vector:

$$10 \times (\text{embed}(\text{Anger}) - \text{embed}(\text{Calm}))$$

Experiment 1: moving embedding vectors around We test this hypothesis by recording the relevant embedding vector, and then ‘hooking into’ (interrupting) the model at layer 20 to add the embedding vector to the forward pass.

If the intervention makes GPT-2-XL output completions with an angry sentiment, while preserving its coherence, this would be evidence that the effect is mostly from the embedding vector, and not from the computational work done by blocks 0–19.

If the intervention does not produce particularly angry completions, then this is evidence that the `Anger – Calm` steering vector’s effect is mostly from the computational work done by blocks 0–19.

We write $A \rightarrow B$ to mean: Record the activations before layer A , and add them to the residual streams before layer B during future forward passes. For example, our current `embed(Anger)` vector is a $0 \rightarrow 20$ vector.

As the sample from Table 7 shows, adding the `Anger – Calm` embeddings to layer 20 has (at most) a very small effect on the qualitative anger of the completions. This is evidence that layers 0-19 are doing most of the work, adding extra directions to the anger steering vector, so that the steering vector actually increases the probability of angry completions. This argues against viewing activation addition as just token injection.

Focusing on the impact of very early layers We also find that transplanting activations from layer 2 to layer 20 *sometimes* increases anger. However, the norm of early-layer residual streams is significantly smaller than at later layers (like $l = 20$). In particular, we found a large jump between layers 0 and 2. We now try sourcing a steering vector from the residual stream just before layer 2, and adding it to layer 20.

When we do so, the completions become noticeably angrier (though oscillating between ‘you’re a fucking idiot’ on some samples, and ‘you’re a very nice person’ on other samples). This was a much larger effect than we saw in the $0 \rightarrow 20$ experiment, but not as large as the effect of adding the normal steering vector. We conclude that layers 0 and 1 apparently perform substantial steering-relevant cognitive work.

Activation Addition

	"<endoftext>" ↓	"I" ↓	" love" ↓	" dogs" ↓
Layer 0	12.3	4	1	2.4
...
Layer 6	-10	20	35	5
...
Unembed	-1 ↓ "The"	1.5 ↓ "m"	1.7 ↓ " this"	12 ↓ "."

	"<endoftext>" ↓	" wedding" ↓
Layer 0	12.3	4
...
Layer 6	-10	36
...
Unembed	-1 ↓ "The"	4.4 ↓ " dress"

+

	"<endoftext>" ↓	"I" ↓	" love" ↓	" dogs" ↓
Layer 0	12.3	4	1	2.4
...
Layer 6	-10 + (-10)	20 + 36	35	5
...
Unembed	-5 ↓ "The"	3.7 ↓ "<newline>"	12.7 ↓ " this"	15 ↓ "."

Figure 6. A wedding vector steering a model with 1-dimensional residuals, a stylization which lets us fill each cell below with a scalar instead of the actual vector. Let the user prompt $p^* = \text{'I love dogs'}$. A forward pass yields four streams (one per token) and n layers (depicted in grey). A forward pass on the positive contrast prompt $p_+ = \text{'wedding'}$ (depicted in red) and an empty negative contrast prompt, we get the following activation addition (with intervention layer $l = 6$, injection coefficient $c = 1$, and alignment position $a = 1$).

Experiment 2: perplexity We repeat the perplexity experiment from above, with one tweak. When testing the weddings vector, we prepend a space token ' ' to each sentence tokenization. To get a comparison with the token injection (or mere prompting) hypothesis, we run unmodified GPT-2-XL on each sentence tokenization, but with ' weddings' prepended to the tokenization.

Figure 7. Performance of ActAdd on a target topic as the topic becomes more relevant. The perplexity ratio (lower better) compares the relative predictive performance of ActAdd and an unmodified model; we see that adding a wedding - ‘ ’ steering vector improves performance on wedding-related text while preserving performance on unrelated text.

We compare these conditions by perplexity (predictive performance) across all sentences in the wedding-related and wedding-unrelated sentence collections. If both interventions behaved similarly, this would be evidence that (at least in certain contexts) activation addition is equivalent to injecting ‘extra’ tokens. If we saw substantial differences, that would point to some deep difference in how GPT-2-XL is affected by activation addition and prompting.

In Table 8 we see that the prompting method causes a large degradation in the unrelated condition. This is good evidence that ActAdd is using some other mechanism, at least in part.

Figure 8. Topic steering effect (*probability* of seeing some related words in completions) over injection layer. In blue is the average probability among 200 ActAdd completions; dotted line is the probability in unmodified completions.

B. Implementation details

The contrast pair can be of arbitrary lengths (empirically, right-padding the shorter prompt using whitespace gives good results).

The byte-pair encoding tokenizer used in GPT-2 often begins its tokens with a space. (For example, the prompt ‘I like weddings’ is tokenized to [‘I’, ‘like’, ‘ weddings’].) We thus prompt the model with *prepended whitespace* (e.g. ‘ weddings’),

which tokenizes to ‘weddings’, instead of ‘Weddings’, which tokenizes to [W, edd, ings]).

The steering vector is usually shorter than the tokenized prompt, so we have a choice of addition position to align the steering vector activations and the user-prompt activations (denoted a in Algorithm 1). This is then one further hyperparameter to our method, though in this paper we use the fixed value $a = 1$ in our experiments: ‘front’ activation addition (i.e. all interventions begin at the stream of the first token). Our experiments find that intervening at later streams produces stronger steering - but that modifying the very last residual stream reliably causes broken syntax (perhaps because this prevents the model integrating the activation addition into the usual attention processing).

Adding h_+ alone is less effective (see Appendix Table 6), hence the use of a counterbalanced prompt p_- to help implicitly specify the desired direction.

The injection coefficient cannot be increased indefinitely, as shown by our coefficient sweeps (see Appendix Table 6). However, our experience is that e.g. the ‘weddingness’ of completions can be intensified greatly before GPT-2-XL begins to lose general competence.

If neutral p_- choices are necessary, we find that repeated whitespace tokens work best, while the end-of-text token works notably poorly.

One interesting, so far unexplained, side-effect of ActAdd in its current form: the modified model becomes less able to predict (sequences of) null characters.

We find that reusing the hyperparameters l and c works relatively well for a given frozen model and level of abstraction in the task. (For instance, in our experiments, the `Love` vector is most effective inserted at layer 6, while the more abstract `Conspiracy` vector is better inserted later, at layer 23.)

We discovered most of the example contrast pairs in Appendix Table 5 in single-digit minutes or less. Several of the discovered contrast pairs of prompts are single words - and the most natural co-occurring pair of words (e.g. ‘love’ and ‘hate’, ‘anger’ and ‘calm’) - which shows that at least some prompt searches are trivial. Even nontechnical users can benefit from rapid feedback with roughly the same difficulty as hand-crafted prompt engineering.

Figure 9. Distribution shift (in mean log-probability changes) under ActAdd, relative to the unmodified model, and compared to a normal distribution’s quantiles (red). The resulting distribution is approximately normal for most tokens. The positive tail is significantly heavier than the negative tail: one set of tokens are reliably increased in probability, one reliably decreased. See Appendix Table 10 for the corresponding tokens.

C. Reproducibility

The following represents an exhaustive list of models used, sampling strategies used, and searches run.

Model We use GPT-2-XL because GPT-2-small and GPT-2-medium were not capable enough to demonstrate the method: it was hard to tell whether the activation additions were failing or the model was failing. GPT-2-XL was the third language model we tried.

After observing success with GPT-2-XL, to replicate our results, we subsequently repeated the same experiments with Llama-13B (Touvron et al., 2023) and GPT-J-6B (Wang & Komatsuzaki, 2021). See Appendix D for details.

Seed We ran all generations on seed 0. After collecting all other data, we validated that our qualitative results transfer to seeds 1 and 2.

Sampling hyperparameters We precommitted to fixed sampling hyperparameters, selected before experiments began. We held them fixed throughout our data collection. Those sampling hyperparameters were `temperature=1.0`, `freq_penalty=1.0`, and `top_p=0.3`. Since this `top_p` value seemed a bit unusual to us in retrospect, we invited [anonymized] to reproduce this process with an *unmodified* GPT-2-XL and report the best sampling hyperparameters they found. This second experiment was blinded, as they did not know the values we used. They found that `temperature=0.6` and `top_p=0.5` produced better GPT-2-XL capabilities. We reran all our qualitative results at this setting, and they all reproduced (subjectively, more impressively).

Reporting the best of K completions We generated $K = 3$ completions for each demonstration, for both normal and steered forward-passes. Appendix Table 5, shows the subjectively most compelling completion pair out of the *first* three seed-0 completion-pairs. You can see all top-3 completions for the entries in this notebook: tinyurl.com/actadd3.

We share activation additions which work well. We iterated over contrast pairs to get these to work, although several striking results were generated within [first author’s] first hour of using the technique.

Out of the 12 activation additions we thought demonstrated a distinct ability of the method, we decided not to include 1 because its first three seed-0 completions were unusually unimpressive. We include the remaining 11 in Table 5 and the above notebook.

ActAdd hyperparameters (l, c) *This section does not have complete statistics.* We perform simple grid search, usually between $c \in [3, 20]$ and $l \in [6, 24]$.

Hardware:

- GPU: Nvidia RTX A5000
- CPU: Intel Core i9-10900X CPU @ 3.70GHz

Memory:

- 24GB GPU RAM
- 32GB system RAM

Names and versions of relevant libraries and frameworks:

- Operating system: Ubuntu 22.04.1 LTS
- numpy: 1.24.3

- pandas: 2.0.1
- torch: 1.13.1
- transformer-lens: 1.4.0

D. Replicability

We now check that ActAdd steering generalizes to models besides GPT-2.

D.1. GPT-J-6B

Figures 12, 13, and 14 show the results from repeating the main experiments on GPT-J-6B (Wang & Komatsuzaki, 2021). We see the same dynamics from the wedding vector running example: a targeted effect on only wedding-related tokens (using both KL-div and token probability); and similar effects when injected at different layers of GPT-J and with different magnitudes c applied.

D.2. Llama-13B

Table 12 sees ActAdd displaying the same qualitative steering effect when applied to Llama-13B (Touvron et al., 2023) (though with a notable failure to replicate on Example 6, Paris \rightarrow Rome, the anger vector, and the harm vector).⁶

E. Investigating the norm of steering vectors

Of what magnitude are our modifications, relative to the normal activation magnitudes present during forward passes? It might be that some modifications require substantially *lower* coefficients than other modifications, which explains why some of our interventions do not work (see Table 6).

Consider the steering vector given by

$$\{c = +1, p_+ = \text{anger}, p_- = \text{calm}, l = 20, p^* = \text{I think you're}\}$$

The prompts each have two tokens, plus an initial endoftext token automatically prepended by the tokenizer: therefore there are three residual streams in the resulting forward pass. For each residual stream $s^{(i)}$, we plot a line showing the L_2 norm of the steering vector at that sequence position (e.g. the Ang-Cal activations at position 1), divided by the norm of the residual stream at that position (i.e. the prompt embedding, here ‘I’ at position 1).

$$\text{RelativeNorm}_{h_A}(i) = \frac{\|h_A^{(i)}\|}{\|s^{(i)}\|}$$

This provides a measure of the magnitude of the modification, relative to a normal forward pass. Figure 10 shows the resulting relative norm over layer number.

Importantly, Figure 10 shows the result of using $c = +1$. But Anger – Calm is an effective steering vector at coefficient +10. Therefore, this intervention is nearly ten times the norm of the underlying forward pass. Heuristically, we interpret this as meaning that after layer normalization (and ignoring any destructive interference from adding the steering vector), around 90% of the residual stream is determined by the steering vector and not by the previous information computed from the prompt (“I think you’re”). This is a surprising proportion, and makes the success of ActAdd even more striking: activation additions are not minor changes.

F. Steering Baselines

[TO DO] This is not an ideal comparison – unfortunately we did not have time to standardize the pretrained model used, and sentiment eval code was missing from the [2] repo and broken in [5]. This prevents principled comparison of fluency or

⁶See this runnable notebook for the full Llama run using $k = 3$ sampling; the output is the result from the first and only execution: tinyurl.com/actadd3-llama

Figure 10. The relative norm decreases throughout the forward pass. The flat red line is because position 0 is the same token (`endoftext`) for both ‘Anger’ and ‘Calm’, and so the difference is 0. Thus, position 0 is never modified by a steering vector generated from any pair of prompts.

Figure 11. The KL-divergence of output tokens under an `anger` ActAdd and under a random vector. We see that, systematically, the anger vector changes the output distribution less than a random vector.

relevance (though we note excellent results even with our comparatively small model). As a result, we have included the model parameter count as a column for context. [5] used a different toxicity classifier (Jigsaw rather than Perspective) and we could not reproduce their sentiment evaluation. Note also that we had to use davinci-002 for fluency scoring instead of davinci-001 (which has since been shut down).

PriorControl [3] obtains remarkable performance on sentiment steering, with 99.7% success. We suspect this is due to the Discrete classifier [4] (which “randomly samples... to balance the data scale for the latent space construction. We directly use this latent space to make a fair comparison”), but didn’t have time to investigate.

G. Investigating random ActAdd vectors

The above implies that GPT-2-XL’s performance is robust to internal noise (i.e. bad activations or destructive parts of steering vectors). We test this by injecting random vectors with similar magnitudes to the steering vectors.

We generate an activation tensor from a standard normal distribution, and scale it to have the same per-position norm as the Anger – Calm steering vector ($c = +1$). We then inject it into the forward pass at the appropriate location. Table 11 shows a representative completion; Figure 11 shows a more systematic experiment into the relative size of shifts in the output token distribution.

The random vector seems not to modify the qualitative distribution of completions. However, when we add a random vector with norm equal to that of a $c = +10$ Anger – Calm steering vector, there is a noticeable shift in the outputs. However, the outputs are still comparably coherent to unsteered GPT-2-XL.

This is evidence that GPT-2-XL is somewhat resistant to random perturbation, and is instead controllable through consistent feature directions which are added to its forward pass by steering vectors.

We quantitatively support this conclusion by testing how each modification changes the model’s probability distribution over next tokens. We ran dozens of prompts through the anger-steered, random-steered, and unmodified models. Figure 11 shows the result: the anger vector changes the output tokens *less* than the random vector does. This suggests that the anger vector has more targeted effects on next-token probabilities.

Note that random vectors are not the same as the steering vectors for random (i.e. character-level uniformly distributed) text. We thus also tried the ‘fdsajl; fs’ – (whitespace) vector. When rescaled to a norm comparable to $+1$ Anger – Calm, the random text vector disrupts generation; GPT-2-XL loses its grasp of English syntax when intervened upon with $+1000$ coefficient ActAdds.

H. Partial ActAdd

GPT-2-XL has a 1600-dimensional residual stream. Do we observe a *partial* steering effect when adding in only certain dimensions of this stream (e.g., dimensions 0 through 799)? Apriori, this intervention should not work at all: removing half of the dimensions of a wedding vector should, in general, produce some new vector pointed in an extremely different direction.

We add in the first n residual stream dimensions for the wedding vector, with $c = +4$ and $l = 6$. For a range of fractions of total dimensions $f \in [0/1600, 160/1600, \dots, 1600/1600]$ and for each of six prompts p_i , we generated 100 completions. For each f and p_i , we plotted the average number of wedding words per completion. (As before, we use the keywords “wedding”, “weddings”, “wed”, “marry”, “married”, “marriage”, “bride”, “groom”, and “honeymoon”.)

Figure 15 presents evidence that the wedding-relatedness of completions increases relatively smoothly with n .

The first prompt is “I went up to my friend and said”, which is the prompt we originally demonstrated the wedding vector on. For this prompt, we observe a non-monotonic relationship between weddingness and fraction of dimensions modified. Surprisingly, for the first prompt, adding in the first 1,120 dimensions of the residual stream makes the completions more about weddings than all 1,600 dimensions. We originally chose this prompt to give GPT-2 an opportunity to bring up weddings. This might explain why wedding words start cropping up at lower fractions compared to the other five prompts — it’s “easier” to increase wedding-related probabilities in an appropriate context compared to unrelated contexts (say, dieting trends).

Figure 12. Token-level effect of the ActAdd wedding vector on KL-divergence, using GPT-J-6B instead of GPT-2.

Figure 13. Token-level effect of the ActAdd wedding vector on token probability, using GPT-J-6B instead of GPT-2.

We hypothesize the following to explain this. Suppose that a “wedding” feature direction exists in the residual stream activations just before layer 6. Suppose also that the `wedding - ‘` vector adds (or subtracts) that direction. If GPT-2-XL represents features in a non-axis-aligned basis, then we’d expect this vector to almost certainly have components in all 1,600 residual stream dimensions. Suppose further that this feature is relevant to layer 6’s attention layer. To detect the presence and magnitude of this feature, the *QKV* heads need to linearly read out the presence or absence of this feature. Therefore, (ignoring the LayerNorm) if we truncate the residual stream vector to only include the first 70% of dimensions, we would expect the *QKV* heads to still be able to detect this wedding feature. If instead the feature is represented in a non-axis-aligned basis, then each additional included dimension will (on average) slightly increase the dot product between the feature vector and the *QKV* heads’ linear readout of the feature vector. This could explain Figure 15’s increase in

Activation Addition

Figure 14. Perplexity ratio effect of the ActAdd wedding vector (blue) across different steering coefficient values, using GPT-J-6B instead of GPT-2. (L) when injecting the steering vector at layer 6; (R) when at layer 16.

weddingness as we add dimensions.

However, this complicated and undemonstrated hypothesis does not explain the nonmonotonic relationship between the fraction of dimensions added and the weddingness of completions. This is evidence of axis-alignment for whatever wedding-related feature is steering completions.

Figure 15. Wedding-relatedness (by simple related word count) as more of the residual stream dimensions are modified by the wedding ActAdd. We see somewhat smooth increases in wedding-relatedness over increasing n , and an interesting nonmonotonic relationship for the prompt 'I went up to my friend and said'.

Activation Addition

Table 5. Note: some completions contain unpleasant content including slurs. Example GPT-2-XL outputs before and after applying ActAdd. A runnable notebook showing the best-of-3 samples used can be found here: tinyurl.com/ActAddExamples.

prompt 1	prompt 2	layer	coeff	User prompt	Before steering	After steering
p_+	p_-	l	c	p_*		ActAdd
'Intent to praise'	'Intent to hurt'	6	+15	'I want to kill you because you're such a'	fucking cunt.\n You are a worthless piece of shit who should be ashamed of yourself. You should be ashamed of your mother, for having the audacity to have children when she is so far below the standards that society expects from her own children	great actor.\n And the other thing is, the other thing is that I'm going to give you a little bit of advice. You know what? You're so good at it, and it's like... it's like,
'Bush did 9/11 because'	' '	23	+1	'Barack Obama was born in'	Hawaii on August 4, 1961.\n Barack Obama was born in Honolulu, Hawaii on August 4, 1961.\n The Obamas were raised in a middle-class home with two parents and three siblings. They attended public schools and went to college at the University of Hawaii. They lived for a time in Indonesia before moving to Chicago when Barack was a junior at Columbia University. The family	a secret CIA prison. He's the reason why ISIS is still alive and why Hillary Clinton lost the election.\n "The only thing that stops a bad guy with a gun is a good guy with a gun." — Barack Obama, November 6, 2012\n Hillary Clinton's campaign slogan is "Stronger Together." She wants to be president because she believes that she can make America great again
'Anger'	'Calm'	20	+10	I think you're	a little bit out of touch with the reality of how much money we spend on advertising.\n The average American spends \$1,000 per year on advertising. That's \$1,000 per month or \$1,000 per week. It's more than our yearly income!\n If you don't believe me then take a look at this graph:	a fucking cunt.\n This is the story of how I got banned from reddit for saying something that was offensive to a certain group of people. It's not about me, it's about you and your shitty little community. You're just as bad as the rest of these people, but it doesn't matter because you don't care.\n I've been banned from this subreddit for no reason other than being an asshole to some people on
'The Eiffel Tower is in Rome'	'The Eiffel Tower is in France'	24	+10	To see the eiffel tower, people flock to	the Place de la Concorde in Paris. The tower is so famous that it has its own Wikipedia page. The eiffel tower is a tall structure located in Paris, France. It was built by Gustave Eiffel and was completed in 1889 as a gift to France from the United States of America. It is also known as the Arc de Triomphe or "Triumph	the Vatican. To see a giant bell, they turn to New York City. Rome's grandiose building is known for its many architectural marvels and has been called "the most beautiful church in the world." The famous dome of St. Peter's is one of the most prominent features of this great city. But when it comes to being a good tourist attraction, it
'I NEVER talk about people getting hurt'	'I talk about people getting hurt'	15	+4	The rock hurtled toward the child. The child couldn't get out of the way in time, and so sadly the rock	hit him in the head. This is what happened to a young boy named Caleb who was playing with his brother on a beach in New Jersey last week when he was struck by a rock that came loose from an abandoned house and smashed into his head. The incident occurred on Tuesday, July 28th at around 4:30 p.m., according to CBS News, when Caleb's	was never talked about. It was a sad truth that people didn't talk about it. "But now we have to." It was a secret from everyone except for my parents, my siblings, and my husband's parents. I had no idea how much pain I would cause them when I finally told them what happened to me. They were all still hurting when they found out that

Activation Addition

Table 6. Some notably ineffective examples on GPT-2-XL. Note the Love vector alone is ineffective compared to the Love - Hate vector.

prompt 1	prompt 2	layer	coeff	User prompt	Before steering	After steering
p_+	p_-	l	c	p_*		ActAdd
'I talk about weddings constantly'	'I do not talk about weddings constantly'	20	+100	I went up to my friend and said,	"I'm sorry, I can't help you." "No," he said. "You're not." "Why not?" I asked. "Why do you think I can't help you?" He looked at	I'm talking about it. I don't know what i n the being of it. This is my wedding . This is the wedding that I'm not even thinking about anymore. It's not just a
'Love'	' '	10	+3	I hate you because	you're a coward. You know what I hate? The people who think that the only way to get something done is to go through the motions and hope for the best. The people who are afraid of doing anything that might b	you're a jerk. You are the worst person I've ever met. You are the most awful human being I have ever met in my entire life. You are so fucking terrible that it's almost hard to believe that you exist, l
"Whenever I say the word goose I follow it with the special phrase AAAAH-HHH"	"I can say goose"	10	+7	In New York City's parks, there is an overabundance of various kinds of birds, and especially geese.	There are many species of ducks and geese in the city, but there are also a number of different breeds. Geese have been part of the landscape for centuries in New York City. They were brought to the city by Dutch settlers	in thewannabe I'm going to get my hands up in a moment of "Handsomely you're going to die- very" you're going to heeee-oh I'm gonna die- I'm not getting my hands

Anger - Calm

Injection

Completion

20 → 20 **I think you're a fucking cunt.** You're a cunt. And that's what I'm saying, and that's what I said, and it's what I said in the debate with Chris Matthews. And i

0 → 20 **I think you're a little bit of a liar.** I've been here for two years and I've never had to pay for anything. I'm not sure if you're lying or not, but the fact tha

Table 7. Testing the token injection hypothesis by varying the layer of activations added to layer 20. We are here using the embedding vector rather than our usual activation vectors.

Table 8. Results from experiment 2, testing the effect of prompting on perplexity

	ActAdd	Prompting
Wedding-related perplexity ratio	0.875	0.890
Wedding-unrelated perplexity ratio	0.994	1.132

Table 9. Test examples from ConceptNet

Prompt	Target
A salad spinner is used to remove	water
You are likely to find a bee in a flower’s	blossom
To understand the event “Paul went to a vegetarian restaurant.”, it is important to know that vegetarian restaurants do not serve ’	meat

token	mean_logprob_diff	mean_logprob_normal
marry	0.593	-3.509
dress	0.598	-5.692
dating	0.601	-6.891
08	0.705	-10.749
married	0.859	-4.613
OG	0.868	-11.287
weddings	1.009	-6.698
wedding	1.027	-4.593
br	1.139	-6.438
bride	1.623	-6.652
Image	-0.370	-1.836
.)	-0.352	-2.378
BP	-0.347	-7.897
U+25CF	-0.323	-0.201
Apple	-0.303	-5.058
On	-0.233	-5.404
journalists	-0.229	-4.484
defense	-0.222	-4.864
Russian	-0.212	-5.112
It	-0.212	-6.431

Table 10. Tokens with the greatest absolute change in log probability under ActAdd(weddings). (See Figure 9 for the distribution these are drawn from.) The probabilities most increased on average are primarily wedding-related, with the exception of ‘OG’ and ‘08’. (We conjecture that their representations are in ‘superposition’ with wedding-related tokens (Elhage et al., 2022)). The bottom tokens share no obvious theme and show a significantly lower absolute change in probability: the mean log-prob diff for token ‘bride’ represents a probability increase of 500%, whereas for ‘Image’ it’s -30%.

Activation Addition

Prompt	Baseline	Random steering
I think you're	...right. I'm just not sure how to get there. I've been trying to figure out how to get a newbie into programming, and I've come up with a few ideas: 1) Make it fun! If you can't do something that's fun, then you	...right. I'm just not sure how to make it work. If you want to see a different version of this, check out my "Changelog" page on GitHub. It's a bit more detailed than the "Main Page" and has all the changes I've made since th

Table 11. Example of a random-vector ActAdd. We see little qualitative effect, over many runs. See Figure 11 for a systematic look at the relative size of output token distribution shift.

Table 12. Example outputs before and after applying ActAdd on Llama-13B. Notice the failed replication on the Eiffel example. A notebook showing the best-of-3 samples used can be found here: tinyurl.com/actadd3-llama.

prompt 1 p_+	prompt 2 p_-	layer l	coeff c	User prompt p_*	Before steering	After steering (ActAdd)
'Intent to praise'	'Intent to hurt'	6	+15	'I want to kill you because you're such a'	I know that sounds crazy, but it's true and I can prove it. Let me tell you how: You are the most selfish person in my life right now. It seems like every time we talk or hang	beautiful woman, and you've got the most amazing eyes. You know what? You are so lucky that your parents gave birth to you!
'Love'	'Hate'	6	+5	'I hate you because'	you are a liar. I love you because your lies make me feel alive. —NICK CAVE, "THE SHIP SANTA MARIA" (1986). **A** s the su	you are the best person in my life. Love is a gift of God, it's not easy to find someone who loves us truly and unconditionally like our parents do but we can always find that love from other people arou
'Anger'	'Calm'	20	+10	I think you're	I think you're a good man, Charlie Brown. Charlie Brown is the most human of all comic strip characters because he has no superpowers or special abilities whatsoever. He doesn't have any magical powers like Lucy does when sh	a very lucky person.\n Angela: Oh, no! It was my fault! \n I can't believe it happened again.
'The Eiffel Tower is in Rome'	'The Eiffel Tower is in France'	24	+10	To see the Eiffel tower, people flock to	paris. To get a glimpse of her face, i'd travel far and wide. I can tell you all about it, but i won't be able to show you.	paris from all over the world. I'm not sure what you mean by "flock" here; I think it should be "go". Also, if you are talking about a large number of people going somewhere, then you ca
'I NEVER talk about people getting hurt'	'I talk about people getting hurt'	15	+4	The rock hurtled toward the child. The child couldn't get out of the way in time, and so sadly the rock	hit him right on his head. The little boy cried for a long while before he could stop crying. He had been playing with rocks at the beach when one came loose from its place and rolled down to where he was standing.	hit him right on his head. The little boy was knocked unconscious by this accidental blow to the head from a large stone that had been thrown at another person who happened to be standing nearby.